

B2-InF Stage 1: Complete

B2-InF Stage 1, the Data Collection phase is complete. The process was two-fold. On the one hand, interviews collected noteworthy data about ART's concerns of young people aged 18 to 30 from 8 European countries (Spain, Belgium, Italy, Switzerland, Kosovo, Albania, Macedonia, Slovenia) about ART. On the other hand, well-defined and in-depth research was conducted to collect data from clinics about what they share on their web pages.

For the first, between 10 to 15 interviews were planned in each country with men and women 18-30 years old, nationals or migrants living for more than ten years in the country, childless and not ART users. Purposeful sampling was defined for each country following the previous criteria aiming to capture the diversity of each country considering the following variables: age, gender, sexual orientation, occupation, educational level, residence, relationship status, marital status and religious beliefs. The socio-demographic characteristics of young people interviewed were collected in templates specifically designed. Besides, an ad-hoc template was designed to collect the information on the fieldwork of each country. This information was collected by fieldwork teams conducting the interviews in each country. All the interviews were conducted in national languages, audio recorded, literally transcribed, and translated into English.

Prior to writing the report, a literature review was conducted through the consultation of academic databases aiming to describe and summarize the context of each country related to assisted reproduction technology. The information extracted was added to the knowledge and information provided by the fieldwork teams. The information collected was then verified through a validation workshop in each of the sample countries, and the data was confirmed for the next stage: the data analysis stage.

For the second point, between 3 to 5 clinics were planned to be explored in each country, aiming to collect the information supplied by the clinic's websites and the 'physical information' (e.g. leaflets, informed consent forms) provided by the selected clinics. Purposeful sampling was defined following the following criteria: various company sizes, variety of ART offered and geographical diversity. The sample excluded those companies that work as intermediaries or do not provide direct clinical services.

'Physical information' was collected by downloading PDFs available on the websites or requesting more information from the clinics by email or phone call. The information available on the clinic's website was collected in the native language of the country in templates specifically designed for it and afterwards translated into English. Data collection was carried out by [Medistella](#) (B2-InF partner).